

NEW ARAMID DEVELOPMENTS FOR AEROSPACE/AIRCRAFT APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

New technical developments of Kevlar® and Nomex® aramid fibers and their usage in the aircraft/aerospace industry are reviewed.

Improved Kevlar® 49 fibers, with higher tensile strength (600 Ksi) and a proprietary fiber surface modification for tailored adhesion in composites is being developed. Using this technology a new aerospace product that gives up to 50% improvement in pressure vessel performance (PV/W) is developed. A new thin (2 mils), lightweight (0.8 oz/yd²) fabric made from 55 denier Kevlar® 49 is being used for high performance printed circuit board. Shorter (1/32 - 1/4 in.) Kevlar® fiber forms, with unique reinforcing and wear capabilities have been developed. Spunlaced sheet structures of blends of Nomex® and Kevlar® with a fabric like cohesion and dimensional stability are now available.

Commercially available phenolic fabric prepregs of Kevlar® 49 are characterized and found to meet aircraft interior requirements in peel strength, smoke and off-gases. Kevlar® radomes are found to offer lighter weight and better dielectric properties than glass at all humidity levels. A novel concept of wrapping rods of epoxy/Kevlar® 49 with Kevlar® 49 yarn, gives super tough, high compressive strength rods.

Introduction

Use of aramid fibers in the aircraft/aerospace industry is growing. This growth is bringing a broad research and development effort ranging from basic polymer studies which will yield the new higher performance fibers of the future to the more immediate efforts aimed at improved aramid products and new aramid applications technology. In this paper we will highlight some of the near term aramid research and development with emphasis on its utility in aircraft/aerospace applications. We will first cover new, improved fiber products and then some new applications technology.

NEW FIBER TECHNOLOGY

Performance of aramide fibers in composites is highly dependent of fiber strength and fiber matrix adhesion.

Tensile Strength

High specific tensile strength is a very important property of Kevlar® aramid fiber. Recently, we developed a new higher tensile strength, (600 Ksi) Kevlar® 49 fiber. This new fiber is 20%

higher in strength than standard Kevlar® 49, and 10% higher than aerospace grade Kevlar® 49 roving, (Table 1). Toughness, area under the stress-strain curve, of this higher strength product is improved by 20 to 40%.

TABLE 1

HIGHER TENSILE STRENGTH KEVLAR® 49 ARAMID FIBER

KEVLAR® 49	TENSILE STRENGTH* (MPSI)	RELATIVE TOUGHNESS**
COMMERCIAL		
1420 denier	500	1
4560 denier (aerospace grade)	550	1.2
<u>T-981</u>		
1140 denier	600	1.4
4560 denier roving	600	1.4

* ASTM D2343, epoxy impregnated strand strength

** Area under stress-strain curve

Adhesion

The nature of the fiber-resin interface in Kevlar® composites is especially important and perhaps more complex than that of carbon and fiberglass¹. With Kevlar® the optimum level of adhesion depends upon the specific composite function.

In cases where tensile strength and modulus are the key design criteria, a moderate adhesion level leads to improved performance. Fig. 1 shows a maximum in the relationship of strand tensile strength and short beam shear strength.

In cases where stiffness and shear strength are the key design criteria, higher levels of adhesion are required.

For this reason we have developed a fiber surface modification technology which allows tailored fiber-resin bonding. A patented technology is being incorporated in fiber manufacture. Improved adhesion in unsaturated polyester and in 350°F cure epoxies is shown in Table 2. This technology also improves uniformity and consistency of shear strength.

FIG. 1

Tensile Strength vs. SBSS
(Isophthalic, Heat Cured Polyester)

TABLE 2

IMPROVED ADHESION

Kevlar® Aramid Yarn	Short Beam Shear Strength, *KPSI	
	Epoxy**	Polyester +
No Activation	7.5	4.3
"Activated"	9.5	10.0

* Unidirectional, 60% fiber volume

**350°F epoxy

+ isophthalic, heat cured

NEW PRODUCTS

Improved Roving for Pressure Vessels (T981)

Understanding Kevlar® aramid yarn-to-composite tensile strength conversion has led to the development of an improved roving for pressure vessels. Only 60-65% of the strand tensile strength of Kevlar® is delivered in a pressure vessel at burst. Adhesion between the Kevlar® fiber and the matrix was shown to be the key variable affecting strength conversion². We found that the maximum conversion of fiber strength to the composite is achieved at a moderate adhesion level, about 2/3 that of standard product. By tailoring adhesion via fiber surface modification, the pressure vessel performance (PV/W) have improved up to 50% (Table 3). Furthermore, this new product (T-981) has superior damage tolerance. In pressure vessels it has twice the damage tolerance of standard Kevlar® and 10 times that of graphite (Fig. 2).

TABLE 3

IMPROVED ROVING FOR PRESSURE VESSELS

Kevlar® 49 Roving	Adhesion (Short Beam Strength MPSI)	Vessel Performance* (PV/W 10 ⁶ in)	Strength Conversion **
Aerospace Grade Roving (T969) (4560 den)	7.5	1.0	65%
T981	5.0	1.4 - 1.5	86%

* 6.6" bottle

** Fiber Strength at Burst/Strand Strength

Low Denier Kevlar® 49

Very thin, lightweight fabric made from 55 denier Kevlar® 49 yarns with only 24 filaments have been developed. Fiber strength, elongation and modulus are typical of Kevlar® 49. Fabric weight is 0.8 oz/yd² and thickness is 2 mils. Using this fabric, we are developing a new lightweight, strong, and stiff composite printed circuit boards where low thermal expansion is required. Kevlar® fabric is ideal for this application since it has low thermal expansion which makes it compatible with leadless ceramic chip technology. A match of board expansion with ceramic is required to avoid in use solder joint failures due to thermal cycling (Table 4).

FIG. 2

PRESSURE VESSELS DAMAGE TOLERANCE

TABLE 4

THERMAL EXPANSION COEFFICIENT OF EPOXY FABRIC COMPOSITES

Composite	In-Plane Expansion (PPM/°C)
Kevlar® 49 Aramid	5-7
E-Glass	15-20
Ceramic Chip Carrier	6

Short Fibers

Previously, short fibers > 1/4 inch were available. New short fiber forms of Kevlar® > 1/32 - 1/8 inch have been developed (Table 5).

TABLE 5

KEVLAR® ARAMID SHORT FIBER PRODUCTS

	Description	Uses
Commercial		
T970A	Staple ≥ 1 inch lengths	Spun yarns and felts
T970B	Chopped fiber ≥ 1/4 inch	Reinforcement Brakes, clutches, plastics
T-979	Pulp Nominal 2-4 mm	Reinforcement Gaskets, brakes, clutches plastics, elastomers
Developmental		
Shorter, chopped fiber	1/32, 1/16, 1/8 inch	Reinforcement molding compounds
"Adhesion Activated"		Reinforcement molding compounds

These straight short fibers are useful to maximize composite modulus, impact resistance, toughness and wear of molded plastic parts. Fig. 3 illustrates a comparison between Kevlar® and fiberglass polyester Bulk Molding Compound in a standard wear test. The bar reinforced with 5% Kevlar® has no wear after 1 million cycles, while the bar reinforced with 12% glass shows severe wear after 0.33 million cycles.

Pulp Reinforced Elastomers

Reinforcement of elastomers with pulp improves their modulus, tensile strength, tear, cut, wear and puncture resistance over a wide temperature range. Uniform dispersion of Kevlar® into elastomers is essential to achieve these improvements and we have developed technology to do that. Applications include rocket case liners, high temperature seals and power transmission belts.

FIG. 3

WEAR RESISTANCE (BULK MOLDING COMPOUND)

TEST

PV = 3490 lb-ft/in.**2-min.

SAMPLES

KEVLAR 29	E-GLASS
5% FIBER	12% FIBER
66% FILLERS	64% FILLERS
1 MILLION CYCLES	0.33 MILLION CYCLES

BOTH SAMPLES USED

1/4 INCH FIBERS
THERMOSET POLYESTER RESIN

Low Density Spunlaced Aramid Sheet Products

A new spunlaced Kevlar® structural sheets with good physical properties, cohesion and dimensional stability is developed by interlacing the fiber under the influence of high pressure water jets. For this reason no binder fibers are used thus, allowing a fabric performance based completely on all-Kevlar® or blends of Kevlar®/Nomex® fiber properties. Another additional advantage is the ability to produce uniform sheets with light basis weights (0.5 to 4.0 oz/sq yd) at low cost and an economical advantage over wovens. Compositions of 100% Kevlar® and up to 50/50 ratio blends with Nomex® show high performance in plastic reinforcements, friction products, thermal and electrical insulation and fire blocking layers.

Recently, the FAA has issued a rule requiring the use of fire-blocking layers for aircraft seats. The regulation is based on "medium-scale fire" test in which mock seats are exposed to 2000°F for two minutes. Seats must exhibit less than 10% weight loss, and flame spread less than one seat width (Fig. 4). Airlines additional requirements include light weight, comfort and a wear life of at least 3 years. A low density spunlaced sheet of blends of Nomex® and Kevlar® aramid fibers (E-89) meets all these requirements. The fire-blocking efficiency of E-89 is further enhanced through layering which allows the total fireblocking layer weight to be minimized. The material does not adversely affect seat comfort and has a wear life greater than 5 years.

FIG. 4
SIDE BY SIDE SEATS

APPLICATIONS TECHNOLOGY

Usage of aramid composites is increasing steadily as the industry learns to capitalize on the special features of Kevlar®. Consequently, new application technology develops.

Phenolic Systems For Aircraft Interiors

Fire retardant epoxies presently used in aircraft interiors generate relatively large amounts of smoke. Alternative phenolic resins offer low flammability and low smoke generation but viewed to have processability and peel strength problems.

Recently, we assessed commercial Kevlar® 49 fabric/phenolic prepreg systems as face sheets on honeycomb panels of Nomex® aramid paper. Several prepreps were found to meet current specifications in peel strength (as-made and after humidity-aging), flammability, smoke and off-gasing by the NBS Smoke Chamber Tests (Table 6). Kevlar®/phenolic interiors are currently in the Airbus A-310, the BAC-146, and to a limited extent in Boeing 767 and 757.

TABLE 6
SMOKE AND GAS EMISSION

Matrix Resin	Smoke	Gas Emission (ppm at 4 min.)					
	D _s	CO	NO _x	HCN	HCL	HF	SO ₂
Epoxy	145	360	33	4	0	0	0
Phenolic	69	273	20	2	0	0	0

*2 plies S-285 Kevlar® 49, Honeycomb Panels.
0.5" Nomex® 3 lb/ft³, 1/8" cell
NBS Smoke Chamber, Flaming Mode, 2.5 waHs/cm²

Radomes

Use of Kevlar® in aircraft radomes is currently limited because of concern over the effect of moisture absorption on the dielectric properties of Kevlar® composites.

We examined the performance of Kevlar® and E-glass in identical epoxy resin laminates under humidity conditions varying from bone dry to complete moisture saturation at 75% R.H (Table 7).

The lower dielectric constant advantage of Kevlar® is maintained at all humidity conditions and the variation in dielectric properties is primarily a function of the matrix resin moisture absorption. These studies are being extended to include measurements at radar frequencies on typical radome constructions.

Radomes reinforced with Kevlar® 49 aramid are currently used on some commercial, and military aircraft such as the Cessna Citation, and the Lockheed C-5A. Acceptable in-service life of 7 to 9 years have been demonstrated. Kevlar® is replacing E-glass which is not only heavier but also has a higher dielectric constant.

TABLE 7

COMPOSITE DIELECTRIC CONSTANT* VS. CONDITIONING

CONDITIONING	COMPOSITE DIELECTRIC CONSTANT	
	Kevlar® 49	E-Glass
Dry, As-Made	4.32	5.38
75% R.H., R.T., 6 months	4.49	5.67
Redried	4.12	5.26
75% R.H., 60°C, 3 months (equilibrium pick-up)	4.42	5.40

*Fabric/Epoxy Composite; 10^6 Hz

Super Tough Wrapped Rods

A novel wrapping concept was developed in the course of our studies of compressive failure modes. This technology involves circumferential wrapping of unidirectional epoxy/aramid rod with epoxy impregnation Kevlar® 49 fiber (Fig. 5). This transfers transverse loads usually carried by the matrix to the wrapping fiber as tensile load. Failure modes involving fibers separating from each other or buckling are delayed since the wrapping fiber strength is much higher than the resin strength. Similarly, compressive load on the core fibers can be transferred to tensile load on the wrapping fibers. The change in rod properties vs. unwrapped pultruded rods can be very substantial. For example, a Kevlar® 49-epoxy rod where 30% of the fibers are in the wrapping, shows the following unique property improvements.

- 3 x increase in the ultimate compressive strength
- 1.4 x increase in Flex strength
- 10 x increase in fatigue life
- 3-4 x increase in elastic limits of compression and flex

Naturally such a rod would have 30% less tensile strength and modulus since 30% of the fibers are in the wraps.

FIG. 5
WRAPPED RODS

The change in compressional behavior is illustrated in Fig. 6 which compares unwrapped pultruded rods of graphite and Kevlar® with a wrapped rod of Kevlar® 49. Note the substantial improvement in toughness (area under the curve). Possible applications for wrapped rods include heavy duty leaf springs, drive shafts, antenna guys, moving industrial equipment parts and crashworthy structures.

FIG. 6

COMPOSITE COMPRESSIVE STRESS—STRAIN CURVES

KEYLAR 49 WRAPPED ROD KEYLAR 49 CONTROL GRAPHITE

Conclusion:

- o The development of new higher strength aramid fiber and a tailored fiber/matrix interphase improves the performance of Kevlar® fiber in many areas, one of which is pressure vessels.
- o New cutting technology makes it possible to have shorter Kevlar® fibers for reinforcement and improved wear of molding compounds.
- o New spinning technology makes a 55 denier yarn and low basis weight fabric possible.
- o New lacing technology make Kevlar® and Kevlar®/Nomex® spunlaced sheets structures possible.
- o Phenolic resin were found to meet all aircraft interior requirements.
- o The dielectric constant of Kevlar® composites is found to be lower than glass at all levels of humidity.
- o Wrapped rods offer unique improvements in Kevlar® compressive and fatigue properties.

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